

Kinetics of Oxidation of Ethoxyethanol by Potassium Permanganate

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The kinetics of oxidation of ethoxyethanol by acid permanganate in presence of sodium pyrophosphate have been investigated. The order of the reaction is one with respect to each of permanganate and ethoxyethanol. The product of oxidation is found to be ethoxyacetic acid. Permanganate ion appears to be the predominant oxidant. A mechanism involving the formation of a free radical initially and permanganate ester subsequently is proposed for the oxidation.

PERMANGANATE is used for the oxidation of a variety of organic compounds¹. In this paper the kinetic study of the oxidation of ethoxyethanol, which has not been carried out before is presented.

Experimental

Reagents

The chemicals used were of A.R. grade and their solutions prepared in doubly distilled water.

Product Analysis

Ethoxyacetic acid was identified as the product of oxidation of ethoxyethanol by an excess of acid permanganate. This was isolated from the reaction mixture by ether extraction. The acid was characterised by its boiling point (observed 207.8°, expected 206-207°) and qualitative analysis. It was estimated volumetrically using sodium hydroxide (Table 1). The base equivalent confirms the identity

[MnO ₄ ⁻]M	[H ⁺]=0.55M		[P ₂ O ₇ ⁻]=0.05M		Unreacted [MnO ₄ ⁻]M
	[S]M	Vol. of 0.21N NaOH consumed ml	Ethoxyacetic acid formed M		
0.261	0.050	23.1	0.047		0.215
0.309	0.070	32.2	0.068		0.243

S is substrate, ethoxyethanol.

of ethoxyacetic acid. The measured refractive index ($n_D^{20}=1.421$) agrees closely with that expected ($n_D^{20}=1.417$) further confirming the product.

Kinetic measurements

The rate of oxidation of ethoxyethanol by acid permanganate is very rapid and to make it measurable a suitable amount of sodium pyrophosphate was added to the reaction mixture. Reaction was followed by quenching aliquots withdrawn at

definite time intervals in acidified KI solution and titrating the liberated iodine against standardized thiosulphate solution. All the reactions were carried out at $30 \pm 0.05^\circ$, unless otherwise specified.

Results and Discussion

The oxidation of ethoxyethanol by permanganate in presence of H₂SO₄ and sodium pyrophosphate induces the reduction of mercuric chloride. This indicates that some reducing intermediate, i.e., a free radical is formed during the reaction². Complete reduction of one mole of permanganate gave one mole of ethoxyacetic acid. The overall oxidation may then be written as

The rate at which permanganate disappears obeys first order rate laws when the concentration of ethoxyethanol is in excess. The first order rate constant does not vary significantly with the initial concentration of permanganate. Hence the order with respect to permanganate is one (Table 2). The order with respect to ethoxyethanol is also one (Table 3). However no linear relationship has been observed between the rate constant and [H⁺] (Table 4).

[Ethoxyethanol]=0.20M [P ₂ O ₇ ⁻]=0.19M		[H ₂ SO ₄]=0.55M	
[MnO ₄ ⁻]M	0.0075	0.013	0.023
k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	3.34	3.17	3.50

[MnO ₄ ⁻]=0.023M,	[H ₂ SO ₄]=0.824M,	[P ₂ O ₇ ⁻]=0.1513M		
[S] × 10 ³ M	5.54	11.08	16.62	21.16
k ₁ × 10 ⁵ sec ⁻¹	1.94	3.40	5.60	7.64
k ₁ /[S] × 10 ⁸ litre mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	3.51	3.07	3.37	3.61

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF [H⁺]

[MnO ₄ ⁻]=0.0129M [S]=0.0514M	[P ₂ O ₇ ⁴⁻]=0.377M Temp.=28.0°				
[H ₂ SO ₄]M	0.3013	0.6025	0.9038	1.2061	
k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	9.98	7.13	6.64	5.58	

The reaction was carried out at different temperatures (20°-35°) and the activation parameters are as follows : ΔH* = 13.8 k cal mole⁻¹, ΔS* = -26.2 e.u. and ΔF* = 21.5 k cal mole⁻¹ (30°).

The addition of Mn(II) ions decreases the rate constant (Table 5). This indicates that MnO₄⁻ is the

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF [Mn²⁺]

[MnO ₄ ⁻]=0.00075M [S]=0.0064M	[H ₂ SO ₄]=0.114M					
[Mn ²⁺] × 10 ⁴ M	2.16	3.24	4.32	5.40	6.48	7.56
k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	1.61	1.57	1.50	1.39	1.28	1.24

predominant oxidant in this reaction. Increasing [Mn²⁺] decreases [MnO₄⁻] by converting the latter to manganic ions². If ethoxyethanol were oxidised by manganic cations and not directly by MnO₄⁻, the reaction should exhibit auto catalysis and an induction period ; neither is noticed. At a very high [Mn²⁺] the rate should be very low but this could not be tested due to the limitation of solubility of Mn²⁺ in the reaction mixture.

That permanganate ion is the predominant oxidant is evident from the effect of [H₂SO₄] on the rate, which decreases due to shifting to the right of the equilibrium,

Increasing [P₂O₇⁴⁻] impedes the rate (Table 6).

TABLE 6—EFFECT OF [P₂O₇⁴⁻]

[MnO ₄ ⁻]=0.0230M [S]=0.554M	[H ₂ SO ₄]=0.824M						
[P ₂ O ₇ ⁴⁻]M	0.208	0.313	0.418	0.477	0.575	0.679	0.888
k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	5.84	5.45	5.14	4.80	4.69	4.60	4.58

This may be due to complexation of intermediate manganese ions, viz. Mn³⁺ and Mn⁴⁺ enhancing their formation with a consequent decrease in the initial concentration of MnO₄⁻. Though MnO₄⁻ appears to be the predominant oxidant, manganic ions may also be involved in the reaction to some extent. Complexation of Mn³⁺ and Mn⁴⁺ by pyrophosphate has been proved to diminish dominantly their oxidising capacity³. This may also be responsible for decrease in the rate on the addition of pyrophosphate. These presumptions are further proved as a decrease in rate constant is observed on the addition of F⁻ (Table 7). The role

TABLE 7—EFFECT OF [KF]

[MnO ₄ ⁻]=0.0129 [S]=0.500M	[H ₂ SO ₄]=0.824M					
[KF]M	0	0.169	0.338	0.507	1.01	1.52
k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	1.62	1.24	1.11	1.09	1.08	1.05

of F⁻ here is similar to that of pyrophosphate ion. If intermediate ions were the predominant oxidants fluoride and pyrophosphate would have completely suppressed the reaction¹. Since such a behaviour has not been observed it may be concluded that permanganate ion is the main oxidant in this reaction.

Mechanism

Permanganate ion in acid medium may accept an electron from an organic substrate to give rise to free radicals¹. Since induced reduction of mercuric chloride is observed in this study it may be assumed that MnO₄⁻ abstracts a hydrogen from ethoxyethanol producing a free radical and HMnO₄⁻. The free radical is assumed to recombine rapidly with HMnO₄⁻ to form an ester. This involves an attendant formation of a C-O bond. The large negative entropy (-26.2 e.u.) substantiates the formation of such an intermediate. In a rate-controlling step the ester may be assumed to break down with a concerted switch of electrons producing ethoxyacetic acid and Mn(III) species. It is likely that Mn(III) species are complexed by pyrophosphate ion or lost due to disproportionation or its involvement as an oxidant subsequently. This mechanism involving the direct conversion of ethoxyethanol to ethoxyacetic acid is consistent with the observation that no aldehyde was detected in the reaction medium during the reaction. Thus the mechanism may be depicted as in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

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